

Government Scheme Monitoring System

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Abstract—Rural development generally refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is considered a "Silver Bullet" for eradicating rural poverty and unemployment, by way of generating demand for a productive labor force in villages. It provides an alternative source of livelihood which will have an impact on reducing migration, restricting child labor, alleviating poverty, and making villages self-sustaining through productive assets creation such as road construction, cleaning up of water tanks, soil, and water conservation work, etc. Which has been considered the largest anti-poverty program in the world. In this paper, based on the secondary data, an attempt has been made to comprehensively understand the development effort to rebuild rural life and livelihood on the basis of various secondary data.

Keywords— Rural Development, Web Application, Mobile App Development

I. INTRODUCTION

Garmin Area Development For the Government of India is for the people of Gramin areas and this project is used by the government to allow the land and sanction the loan for building the house, In this application, there is no monitoring system to monitor the progress of construction of houses under Rural Housing schemes.

To generate real-time statistical reports of the ongoing constructions.

Design a web-based dashboard for monitoring and a native mobile application to track the progress of the construction just by taking a photograph by using the application.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Irregularities in rural housing schemes

Massive irregularities in the implementation of rural housing schemes in the district have come to the fore recently. Many block-level officials are trying their best to provide concrete houses to those ineligible for their vested interest, it was alleged. The names of altogether 72,921 ineligible people have been recommended for concrete houses under the rural housing schemes by the authorities of 14 blocks in the district, sources said.

The state government has decided to provide concrete houses to the people of Cuttack district who were left out of the priority list for the housing schemes.

The state government's decision came in the wake of the massive destruction caused by Cyclone Fani that hit the state on May 3, 2021.

In deference to the district administration's directive to recommend the names of eligible people for obtaining concrete houses, the authorities of 14 blocks had suggested 1, 28, 327 names for inclusion in the housing schemes. However, a survey by the District Rural Development Agency (DRDA) found that the block authorities have recommended the names of 72,921 ineligible people, sources said.

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

There is no monitoring system to monitor the progress of the construction of houses under Rural Housing schemes. Offline inspection is time-consuming and not another mode of inspection. Track the progress of the construction is time-consuming in offline mode. The existing system is completely offline it takes time to process the application of the user. Employs take time to process the user application due to offline processes.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. Aim

To generate real-time statistical reports of the ongoing constructions. Design a web-based dashboard for monitoring and a native mobile application to track the progress of the construction just by taking a photograph by using the application.

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B. Objective

monitoring system for the construction of houses under Indian state Government rural housing schemes is deployed with these two platforms:

- Mobile Application
- Web Portal.

Figure 1: Proposed System

V. RESULTS

A. Web Portal

Figure 2: MORD Page

Ministry of Rural development sets the target of houses to be completed in a particular state.

Figure 3: State User Page

Figure 4: Target Master

MORD user name of the state and state user details for state user login

Figure 5: House Inspection details

Here MORD user adds the name of the state and the detail

of the house inspection detail

Figure 6: District Master

As per the target given by MORD, the state further sets the target for its Districts.

Figure 7: District User Master

State user divide scheme in districts and add the district user login detail which districts user can log in for the further process.

Figure 8: Target User

The state user set the target of the districts and add the scheme name, number of beneficiaries, amount, and target details.

Figure 9: Release Fund Master

State users add the detail about the fund they get from MORD

Dashboard Snapshots (DRDA)

Figure 10: Block Panchayat User Master

As per the target given by State, DRDA further sets the target for Block Panchayats by adding the name of panchayats and panchayat's user details for login.

Figure 11: Target User

DRDA further sets Target by adding the name of the scheme name and the amount of the scheme and some other details.

Figure 12: Report Generation

The report given by the inspector shows here about house level

Figure 13: Funds Received by Beneficiary

The report given by the DRDA about the beneficiary fund received shows here the name and the details of the beneficiary.

Dashboard Snapshots (Block Panchayat)

Figure 14: Block Panchayat (Dashboard)

As per the target given by DRDA, Block Panchayat further sets the target for its Gram panchayats this is a Dashboard of block panchayat.

Figure 15: Inspector Master

Block panchayat users add the detail of the inspector for offline inspection

Figure 16: Generate Pay Order

After the inspector's offline inspection block panchayat user releases the fund.

Figure 17: Grievance master

For adding the detail of beneficiary

B. Mobile Application

Inspection Login

Figure 18: Inspection Login

Inspector login from mobile application for offline inspection

Figure 19: Navigation Bar

Figure 20: Online Inspection

Figure 19 and figure 20 show the Inspector gets the address of the beneficiary after offline inspection and taking photos of the site and upload to the database.

Figure 21: Beneficiary Login

Figure 22: Beneficiary Profile

Figure 21 and figure 22 show the Beneficiary login form mobile application for offline inspection

Figure 23: Payment Status

Figure 24: Grievance Cell

CONCLUSION

Basically, the system being developed is focusing on basic functionalities that are expected by any of the possible users of the system. This software is web-based as well as android software with easily extendible modules. It can be used in any state for distributes funds for making houses.

A user-friendly GUI is provided and all the functionality given in the functional requirement has been implemented. It makes it easy to work of distributes funds under Rural Housing schemes. It will reduce user workload and keep Government files of funds distributed very secure.

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